

EVALUATION OF PRIVACY-PRESERVING AI USING EDGE COMPUTING IN V2X FRAMEWORK

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ABSTRACT

The advent of Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication has ushered in a new era of intelligent urban transportation systems, promising enhanced safety, efficiency, and connectivity. However, the extensive data sharing inherent in V2X networks poses significant privacy challenges. This review paper explores the integration of privacy-preserving Artificial Intelligence (AI) within the V2X framework, emphasizing the role of edge computing as a pivotal enabler. We systematically examine state-of-the-art techniques in privacy-preserving AI, including federated learning, differential privacy, and homomorphic encryption, highlighting their applicability and effectiveness in V2X scenarios. Additionally, we discuss the synergy between edge computing and privacy preserving AI techniques, which collectively mitigate privacy risks while ensuring real-time data processing and decision-making. By analyzing current research trends, technological advancements, and practical implementations, this paper provides a comprehensive overview of the strategies for maintaining data privacy in V2X networks. Our findings underscore the importance of a holistic approach that combines robust privacy-preserving mechanisms with the decentralized capabilities of edge computing, paving the way for secure and efficient intelligent transportation systems.

Keywords: Privacy-preserving AI, Edge computing, V2X communication, Intelligent transportation systems, Federated learning, Differential privacy, Homomorphic encryption, Data privacy, Real-time data processing, Decentralized computing.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid evolution of intelligent urban transportation systems (IUTS) has been propelled by the integration of Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication, a transformative technology enabling vehicles to interconnected with each other and with infrastructure, pedestrians, and networks. V2X communication promises to escalate road safety, reduce traffic congestion, and make better overall transportation orderliness. The V2X framework uses AI for real-time decision-making and predictive analytics, but also raises privacy concerns due to the continuous transmission and processing of personal and sensitive information.

Yet, conventional AI methods often require centralized data collection and processing, which can exacerbate privacy risks. Edge computing is being explored as a potential solution to privacy challenges in V2X systems, balancing AI-driven insights with stringent safeguards. Edge computing reduces the need for substantial data transit to central servers by decentralizing the data processing process is conducted closer to the data source.. This lowers exposure to potential privacy breaches. This paradigm shift not only enhances privacy but also improves latency and bandwidth efficiency, crucial for real-time applications in ITS. This review paper delves into the intersection of privacy-preserving AI and edge computing within the V2X framework[3]. We explore various privacy-preserving AI techniques, such as federated learning, differential privacy, and homomorphic encryption, assessing their applicability and effectiveness in safeguarding sensitive data in V2X environments. Furthermore, we investigate how edge computing can synergize with these AI techniques to create a robust and secure V2X ecosystem. The posterior sections of this paper are meticulous as follows Related work section discuss a compression explanation several journal paper expressing contextualization, identifying gaps and comparison of other methodologies and foundation of future work . Section III discusses on the technologies and services used in the privacy-preserving. Section IV presents V2X framework and lastly the Realtime solution for privacy-preserving using edge computing in V2X framework.

2. RELATED WORK

Strict performance requirements on response time and network bandwidth, as well as an increase in the need for communication, computing, and storage resources, are the logical result of the emergence of vehicle applications and the exponential growth of data. Large volumes of data will be collected by these devices, surpassing centralized cloud infrastructures in terms of processing requirements in real time. Munn (2020) examines the privacy implications of edge computing in a critical manner. In the 5G epoch, edge computing will make a divergence and will greatly promote the application and development of 5G. Rahati-Quchania, Abrishamia, and Feizi (2020) proposed an assignment mechanism called school choice. Under latency limitations, the suggested method delivers the lowest possible cost and energy consumption. The suggested approach can achieve effective and successful compute offloading, as shown by numerical results [2]. The findings can be summed up as follows: as users and devices in the Internet of Things generate ever-larger amounts of data, privacy and security concerns in edge computing environment have grown.

The fifth-generation communication (5G) [17], the next advancement in wireless communication technology, is expected to drastically alter our way of life. Tongyu (2020) first presented the typical 5G application scenarios before going over the fundamentals of new computing models such edge, cloud, and fog computing. These new computations were then taken into consideration and examined in light of the 5G application needs. The period of 5G will be greatly aided by edge computing, which will also greatly accelerate the development and application of 5G. Even though there are numerous ways to offload in MEC, the majority of the time, just one MEC server is used to reduce execution time and energy usage for mobile devices.

A school choice assignment system was proposed by Rahati-Quchania, Abrishamia, and Feizi (2020). Within latency restrictions, the suggested approach achieves the lowest possible cost and energy consumption. The suggested approach can achieve effective and successful compute offloading, as shown by numerical results.

The study "Artificial Intelligence-aided Privacy Preserving Trustworthy Computation and Communication in 5G-based IoT Networks" [12] examines how artificial intelligence (AI) technology can be used to enhance privacy and trust in 5G-enabled Internet of Things (IoT) networks. The study "Artificial Intelligence-aided Privacy Preserving Trustworthy Computation and Communication in 5G-based IoT Networks" looks at how AI technologies can be used to enhance privacy and trust in IoT networks that are enabled by 5G. The research highlights the potential of 5G technology in IoT scenarios like smart healthcare and vehicle networks, but also highlights cybersecurity issues. The authors propose a novel paradigm that combines trustworthy management with privacy protection, enabling secure data processing and communication, and enhancing trust management in computational tasks.

To boost the effectiveness and security of vehicular communication, the study describes a Blockchain-enabled, heterogeneous, 6G-supported [14] safe vehicular management system that employs cloud edge computing. The study, "Edge Computing," describes how to optimize power gain, transmission rates, and local delays in order to lower latency and increase energy economy in vehicular networks. In order to solve car compromise difficulties, privacy preservation—a mechanism that protects against transmission failures, spying, and interruptions—is merged with a consortium blockchain. In order to provide secure data sharing, this model additionally verifies vehicle users during communication. Sections of the study include a review of the research, a discussion of 6G heterogeneity, a modeling of edge computing for vehicle management, a proposed blockchain-enabled privacy-preservation model, experimental findings, and conclusions.

The literature review section of the paper examines current methods for vehicular ad hoc networks (VANETs) [5]. It highlights a narrative of blockchain-based conditional privacy-preserving authentication [16] protocol that harness blockchain technology and public key [15] infrastructure (PKI) to improve security and lessen the processing load associated with private key storage. In the context of blockchain-enabled heterogeneous 6G-supported vehicle management systems. The main disadvantages that were limited Consensus Power In a consortium blockchain, the vehicles involved determine how much consensus power there is. This may limit the blockchain's efficacy and scalability in bigger networks with more participating cars. Overall while the paper presents a promising approach to enhancing vehicular management system, these drawbacks highlight the need for further research and development.

3. TECHNOLOGIES AND SERVICES USED IN PRIVACY-PRESERVING AI

The art of performing data science and build ai solutions aby training or querying on data without the need to collect, distribute or even look at them.

A. Fedearated Learning (FL)

Let's understand standard machine learning, data in collected and curated from one or multiple clients and stored in the cloud storage. The data scientist gets access to these datasets to perform and apply machine learning models on the stored datasets; while doing machine learning [7] the data scientist trains some AI model on the data using machine learning algorithms and model architecture. Once the model has been trained, it is validated against fresh or previously unknown data to make predictions using a validation matrix.

If the model performance is not sufficient, the data scientist makes modifications to the algorithm or the model architecture, which is termed hyper parameter tweaking. Different datasets are added and retrained the algorithm and model architecture. This process is repeated until the proposed algorithm and model architecture works with highest efficiency and potential and it's deployed on the mechanism hence locates the model that will be used to make inference on the device data, this is the classical workflow of the machine learning. The whole proceeding requires the data to mitigate from the client's device to the central server where data-scientist operate in their internal devices leaving the data be risked to be exposed in distinct ways.

Federated Learning (FL) algorithms can train on data without owner sharing or mitigating it. Major components include Cross-device Federated Learning (CDDL) and Cross-Silo Federated Learning (CSFL). CDDL uses millions of devices with sensitive information, while CSFL uses a decentralized server to train models. Each client device then downloads the base model and trains it by learning from the data stored inside each of them. Once the client-side model is trained only the individual model weights are sent to the coordinator server. The coordinator server has a secure aggregator which summarizes the model weights as aggregated focused updates only this aggregated to the model is sent to the data scientist as a combined model using some encrypted communication and the data scientist can use it further improve the initial base model. Finally the data scientist can test the updated model to the new and unseen data which is locally available to them, if the model is unsatisfactory the changes will be imported either in the updated base model architecture or on the improved model and can resend the model to the clients for retraining once completed the combined model performance is satisfactory it is deployed in the client's devices for inference on their respective data therefore using Federated Learning (FL) models are trained on data on millions of devices even though all the training data remains on the devices and no individual updates or identifier information of the device owners required to be stored or shared. The idea of the FL can also be applied trained machine learning models on the data owned by the different institutions. In the CSFL the participant client are not device rather they are hospitals, banks, schools, government institutions etc. Similar as before we can have tens of thousands of these institutions taking part in the training with the huge data set they have for example hospitals can have medical records of tens of thousands of their patients and these data are extremely confidential so the institution do not want to share or exchange information amongst each other or with the central service provider so what we can do is they can use Federated Learning (FL) setting to train and learn a combined model that's going to work well for everyone on their respective private data.

Federated learning, while not guaranteeing complete data privacy, can be combined with other privacy tools like differential privacy, secure multi-party computation (SMPC), and the Homomorphic encryption to prevent data leakage and ensure data security.

Fig. 1. General View of Federated Learning

In the Fig.1 explains the coordination of the training process amongst various client devices is the responsibility of the central server. Model updates are received from the client devices, collected, and then distributed back to the clients. Using its own data, every client device (Client Device 1, Client Device 2, and Client Device 3) trains a local model. Clients update the central server with their trained models. All of the clients' model updates are combined by the central server into a single aggregated model. After that, the combined model is returned to the client devices in preparation for the subsequent training cycle. Without disclosing their raw data to the central server, the client devices can cooperate and learn from each other's data through this iterative process of local training and model aggregation.

B. Differential Privacy

If we think in data owner's point of view from the previously defined FL setup the data owner might have this question, "if I were to reveal the updated model to data scientist what's the maximum amount of private information of the people I may leak" differential privacy helps answering this question. Let's say we have a data set called D and it contains people's data, as a data owner I should ask when querying database D if I remove someone from the database would the output of the query change to answer this question we will make a parallel data set D' by removing or replacing one row from the original data set D now if we make a query to D and D' and if the query result is still same that means that the query result is not conditioned on the removed information and that also means that the information cannot be inferred or retrieved by making these queries. If it is true for all the individuals means the privacy of individual's data in the dataset D is preserved.

Let's consider we want to conduct a survey to know that what percentage of population are smokers so we ask the participants a simple question that "DO you smoke", this information may be sensitive to share and there is a risk that they hide their true response so instead what we can do is we offer them to we make them offer which will ensure that their information will be kept private so what we can do is we can say so that we have one participant bob and bob's answer is "yes" we can ask him to instead of writing his response right away he needs to flip a coin if it's a head he answers yes and if it's a tail he flips a second coin and answer yes if hits and answer no if it's tail. This randomized mechanism makes some level of randomness or noise to bob's real answer there's a 50% chance that bob's response is his real answer, but there's also now a 25% chance that his answer is just outcome of the random coin flip and this simple mechanism gives him an advantage of plausible deniability that means he can any time deny his answer blame it on the coin flip there's no way we can guarantee that bob indeed is a smoker or not.

Now let's see what happens when we don't add the noise mechanism to the data set, in this data set the response can be either 0 or 1 and an attacker wants to know if Bob is smoker or not so he can make sum query to sum the value of all the responses in both D and D' if the sum in D' is 1 less than D that means Bob's response was 1 hence he is a smoker, also note that the maximum difference between the two sums can be at most 1 therefore we can say that the sensitivity of this sum query on D is 1, in other words the sensitivity is the maximum amount that a query changes when removing individual from the database however if we add noise using the coin flip mechanism the attacker cannot be certain if the response they received from bob is a true answer or is the outcome from a coin flip so this mechanism gives a protection to bob's original answer and protects his privacy. However, if the attacker makes multiple queries against D and D' he or she will gradually increase the probability of inferring the right answer about bob to prevent this from happening there's concept called privacy budgeting when we apply as randomized mechanism on the data set or samples it provides a probability distribution of the outcomes the probability distribution when we remove an entry from D the probability distribution slightly changes.

The noise can be added to either on the inputs or on the final output of the query, if it is added to the query result by a curator then it is called global differential privacy (GDP) and if it's added in the individual input then it is called local differential privacy (LDP). In a coin flip example, we offer the participants to add noise to their response therefore it is an example of local dp and if you don't trust in curator, you should choose local dp over global dp on the other hand if you want to minimize the noise introduced to the data set you should GDP over LDP.

The example discussed is a simple randomized mechanism, but mathematically robust noise mechanisms like Laplace, exponential, and Gaussian mechanisms aim to balance accuracy and data privacy, a research area focused on finding the right balance.

C. Homomorphic Encryption

Homomorphic encryption validates computations on encrypted data without accessing plaintext, yielding meaningful results even after encryption. It allows mathematical operations like addition and multiplication to be performed on encrypted data, with decrypted results resembling unencrypted data. Different encryption methods, including Partially Homomorphic Encryption (PHE) [5], Somewhat Homomorphic Encryption (SHE), and Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE), support arbitrary additions and multiplications on ciphertexts.

Homomorphic encryption is a new method for traffic management that protects data privacy while enabling critical computations. It ensures the confidentiality of sensitive data, including vehicle positions, speeds, and routes. Traffic management systems use this encryption to compute average speeds, traffic density, and congestion levels, while maintaining anonymity and ensuring private route information is not disclosed.

Homomorphic encryption offers privacy but also presents challenges in traffic management systems. It's computationally intensive, causing increased processing times and resource demands. Designing algorithms for specific operations is complex, and standardizing protocols for V2X applications is crucial for widespread adoption.

Research focuses on efficient homomorphic encryption systems, privacy-preserving methods, edge computing, and hardware accelerators, requiring collaboration between business, academia, and governmental organizations for intelligent transportation system regulation.

D. Edge Computing

Edge computing is a new paradigm that moves compute and data storage closer to where they are needed, frequently at the network's edge. Unlike cloud computing, which centralizes data processing in huge, faraway data centers, edge computing [1] decentralizes processing power and distributes it to local devices, edge servers, or gateways. This approach is particularly advantageous in latency-sensitive applications, such as the V2X (Vehicle-to-Everything) framework, where real-time data processing is crucial for safety and efficiency. Edge computing involves the deployment of computing resources at the edge of the network, closer to the end users or devices. This architecture reduces the data transmission latency and reduces the bandwidth needed to deliver huge consignment of data to centralized cloud servers. Edge computing can be implemented in various forms, such as edge servers, gateways, or even directly on devices like sensors or IoT nodes.

Fig. 2. Edge computing

In the figure 3 explains that vehicles use sensors to generate data, which is processed by edge nodes near the vehicles. These nodes process the data locally, enabling real-time decision-making. Vehicle-to-Everything communication involves information exchange between vehicles, infrastructure, networks, and pedestrians. Technologies like DSRC and C-V2X are used. Network infrastructure, often 5G, supports high-speed, low-latency communication. Cloud servers handle complex tasks, store data, analyze it, and send updates back to edge nodes, improving the overall system's effectiveness.

4. V2X FRAMEWORK

Emerging technologies such as V2V, V2I, and V2X can transform urban traffic management by allowing real-time data sharing between cars, infrastructure, and road users. Integrating these technologies with intelligent transportation systems, emergency response, and machine learning algorithms can improve safety and efficiency.

Fig. 3. V2X Communication System Architecture

An illustration of Fig.2. explains that, network architecture for automotive communication is shown below. It displays the connections between various vehicle-to-everything (V2X) [3] communication-related entities. The Application Server for Vehicles to Everything. This is the main hub for data processing and sharing between the network and the cars. evolved Node B. a base station responsible for vehicle cellular communication. Unit by the Road. a roadside communication system that enables cars to talk to one other and the network. From vehicle to vehicle. Direct communication between vehicles is meant by this. Infrastructure to Vehicles. Communication between automobiles and roadside infrastructure, like RSUs, traffic signals, and road signs, is referred to here. Car to Pedestrian. This alludes to the exchange of information between moving cars and pedestrians, maybe including safety alerts. Car to Network. This is referring to the exchange of data between automobiles and the network infrastructure. Network for Cloud Radio Access. an architecture for a cloud-based network that increases network efficiency by offloading radio management and processing from base stations to cloud servers.

A cloud computing [2] setting close to the edge of the network that offers V2X apps low latency services. a cloud computing setup that is situated further from the edge of the network. Software-Defined Networking switches enable centralized network administration and control. Network function virtualized. These are scalable and flexible software-based operations that operate on virtualized platforms. The graphic also shows the various communication link types used in V2X, such as cloud-based communication (C-RAN), direct communication (V2V, V2I, V2P, and V2N), and cellular communication (eNB and LTE-Uu).

5. REAL TIME SOLUTIONS FOR PRIVACY-PRESERVING IN EDGE COMPUTING USING V2X FRAMEWORK

The safety of motorists and passengers on the road is greatly enhanced by collision avoidance and safety systems. Real-time detection of probable crashes or hazardous driving circumstances is made possible by these systems, which employ privacy-preserving [19] AI technology to evaluate sensor data locally in cars. Vehicles can make fast choices by utilizing edge computing, which eliminates the need to send sensitive data to the cloud. This improves collision avoidance systems' effectiveness while also offering substantial privacy advantages. Data breaches are less likely when data is processed at the edge, which protects private data like location and driving habits. In general, collision avoidance systems that use edge computing and privacy-preserving [18] AI constitute a significant leap in automotive safety technology.

Modern transportation management must include traffic signal optimization, and edge device integration of AI algorithms has transformed this process. Through the use of V2I connection and real-time traffic data, traffic signals are now able to adjust their timing in order to reduce congestion and enhance overall traffic flow. By handling sensitive car data locally, this creative method prioritizes privacy while simultaneously increasing economy. Personal data is safeguarded from external networks by this system, which encrypts and secures individual information. This development in traffic signal optimization offers a balance between privacy and usefulness that is advantageous to both city planners and drivers, marking a substantial achievement in transportation technology.

AI technology significantly improves the functionality of incident management and emergency response. Vehicles and infrastructure can now communicate in real time [8] with emergency services in the case of an accident or disaster, facilitating a speedier and more effective response. Rapid analysis and response are made possible by edge computing, which also guarantees data security. This implies that all conversations are encrypted to protect confidentiality and that only information that is absolutely necessary is sent to responders. In times of disaster, emergency response teams can better protect and serve the public by employing these cutting-edge technologies.

New technology called Dynamic Route Planning and Optimization enables cars to use privacy-preserving artificial intelligence to find the best routes in real time. The latest traffic data from infrastructure and other cars is received by edge devices, which encrypts and securely processes it to provide this functionality. This approach's main benefit is that it shields private travel information and location data from potential breaches and unwanted access. Users may be certain that their privacy is protected and that optimal route suggestions are still provided by keeping data processing local.

In Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) applications, privacy-preserving [12] AI and edge computing provide several noteworthy benefits. Low latency is one of the key advantages of edge computing since it lowers the need for data transmission to centralized cloud servers, resulting in faster reaction times, which are critical for real-time applications. Furthermore, by processing data locally and utilizing privacy-preserving methods, these technologies improve data security and privacy by shielding sensitive information from unwanted access.

Another significant benefit is scalability, which is made possible by edge computing's capacity to support distributed data processing. This enables the V2X system to grow effectively in response to the growing number of connected cars and gadgets. Additionally, processing data at the edge results in a significant reduction in bandwidth usage, which in turn reduces the quantity of data transferred via networks, thereby lowering bandwidth consumption and related expenses.

Fig. 4. Real-time solutions for privacy-preserving in edge computing using V2X framework.

The Fig.3. illustrates how data moves from a car to a cloud server. Vehicle-to-vehicle, or V2V, communication is used between the car, designated "Vehicle A," and a human. The RSU/Mobile Edge Server, a particular kind of server made to handle data from cars, receives this data after that. After that, the information is transferred via a secure vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I) communication route to a cloud server. Arrows and boxes that represent the many components of the process are used to illustrate it, along with labels that explain each element's role and objective. The illustration emphasizes how infrastructure helps drivers, servers, and cars communicate with one another. Applications like autonomous driving, driver assistance systems, and traffic management are made possible by this information flow.

6. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the integration of privacy-preserving AI techniques with edge computing in the V2X (Vehicle-to-Everything) framework presents significant opportunities for enhancing the security and efficiency of vehicular networks. This review has highlighted several key aspects and challenges associated with implementing such technologies.

Firstly, privacy-preserving mechanisms are crucial for protecting sensitive data transmitted between vehicles and infrastructure, ensuring that user information remains confidential and secure from potential threats. Federated learning, homomorphic encryption, and differential privacy are techniques that have showed promise in securing data while keeping the functionality of AI-driven systems.

Second, edge computing reduces latency and improves real-time decision-making capabilities by processing data closer to the source. By leveraging edge devices, V2X systems can efficiently handle large volumes of data generated by vehicles, leading to faster and more accurate responses to dynamic traffic conditions.

The integration of privacy-preserving AI and edge computing in the V2X framework holds great potential for revolutionizing intelligent transportation systems. However, challenges include interoperability, managing computational resources, and balancing privacy, accuracy, and computational overhead. Future research should focus on developing efficient algorithms and hybrid approaches, requiring collaboration between academia, industry, and policymakers..

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